

Primer: Cross-over Trials

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What is a cross-over trial?

In a two-arm parallel-group randomized controlled trial comparing treatments **A** and **B**, patients are randomly assigned to the two treatment groups. The treatment groups are often treatment (**A**) versus control (**B**). In a cross-over trial each patient receives both treatments **A** and **B** (at different times), i.e. each patient is its own control.

Cross-over designs can only be used if the aim of the therapy is not to cure a condition and if the condition lasts for a long period of time. Chronic diseases such as asthma, migraines, hypertension and epilepsy are conditions for which cross-over designs are particularly well-suited.

The simplest form of cross-over design is the **AB/BA** design. Patients are randomly assigned to two sequences, **AB** or **BA**, and there are two treatment periods.

Sequence group	Period 1	Wash-out	Period 2
1	A	-	B
2	B	-	A

Patients in group **1** receive the treatments in sequence **AB**, while patients in group 2 receive the treatment in sequence **BA**.

In the **AB/BA** design the treatment (with levels **A**, **B**) is factorially combined with the period (**1**, **2**) and this ensures that the period effect can be separated from the treatment effect. If we always gave treatment **A** in period **1** and treatment **B** in period **2**, we could not distinguish whether differences between treatment **A** and **B** are really due to treatment or just due to period.

Periods **1** and **2** are usually separated by a 'wash-out period', during which no treatment is given. This wash-out period should be long enough to ensure that there is no carry-over effect, i.e. that the effects of the treatment given in period **1** do not persist during period **2**. Non-statistical arguments (such as half lives of drugs) should be used to estimate how long treatment effects are likely to persist, and cross-over designs should be avoided if the carry-over effect is expected to be an issue.

Cross-over trials have two major advantages over standard parallel-group trials. First, they help reducing the variability of the treatment effect estimate. As each patient/subject serves as its own control, a larger precision of the treatment effect estimate is obtained. Second, they require a smaller number of patients to detect a treatment effect, but of course two measurements are required per patient.

Example: the Enuresis trial

The Enuresis trial (Hills and Armitage, 1979) is a placebo-controlled drug trial on children suffering from bed wetting. In group **1** ($n = 17$), children are administered the drug for 14 days and the number of dry nights is recorded. Then the placebo is given for the same amount of time and the same outcome is recorded. In group **2** ($n = 12$), children are given first placebo, and then the drug. The following R code shows the outcome in periods 1 and 2 as well as the difference (outcome in period 1 - outcome in period 2) for the first six individuals of the enuresis trial dataset, all belonging to the first group (first drug, and then placebo).

```
head(enuresis)

##   group id outcome1 outcome2 diff
## 1     1  1         8         5    3
## 2     1  2        14        10    4
## 3     1  3         8         0    8
## 4     1  4         9         7    2
## 5     1  5        11         6    5
## 6     1  6         3         5   -2
```

The mean differences is 2.8 nights in sequence group **1**, and -1.3 nights in sequence group **2**. The mean in group **1** (drug - placebo) is positive, suggesting that the number of dry nights is larger with the drug rather than the placebo. The fact that the mean in group **2** (placebo - drug) is negative supports this conclusion. But how large is the treatment effect estimate and its confidence interval and how large is the evidence that the treatment really works?

How to analyse such a trial?

In the **AB/BA** design, the null hypothesis is that the mean differences in the two groups are the same. The analysis can be done using a two-sample *t*-test to compare the two sets of within patient differences. The treatment effect is then estimated as half the difference in mean differences.

```
t.test(enuresis$diff~enuresis$group, var.equal = TRUE)

##
## Two Sample t-test
##
## data:  enuresis$diff by enuresis$group
## t = 3.2925, df = 27, p-value = 0.002773
## alternative hypothesis: true difference in means between group 1 and group 2 is not equal to 0
## 95 percent confidence interval:
##  1.535005 6.612054
## sample estimates:
## mean in group 1 mean in group 2
##      2.823529      -1.250000
```

The *p*-value is 0.0028, indicating strong evidence that the drug has an effect on bed wetting in children. The effect of the drug is estimated as half the difference in means, that is, the treatment reduces the number of wet nights by $(2.8 - (-1.3))/2 = 2.05$ nights (95% confidence interval from 0.77 to 3.31 nights). A paired *t*-test is sometimes used to analyse the paired differences (treatment vs. control) from an **AB/BA** cross-over trial, regardless of the sequence group assignment of each patient. However, this approach is not recommended as leads to a biased effect estimate if the two treatment sequence groups are of different size and there is a period effect.

How to calculate the sample size for an AB/BA trial?

In order to design a cross-over trial, the intraclass correlation coefficient (ICC) needs to be known. ICC is the proportion of the between-patient variance to the sum of between- and within-patient variance (Bland, 2015). Compared to a standard two parallel-group design with $2n$ patients, the **AB/BA** cross-over design only requires $(1 - \text{ICC})n$ patients, so the larger ICC, the smaller the required number of patients. We refer to Senn (2002, Chapter 9.5) for more detailed sample size formulas.

To go further

The **AB/BA** design is extremely popular. However, some trials go beyond a simple comparison between treatment and control and compare three or more treatments for example (Senn, 2002). Cross-over designs may also involve (baseline) measurements before treatment is given.

This document is intended to give a brief introduction to cross-over designs. More detailed information about the analysis, sample size calculation, numerous examples and more advanced aspects can be found in Senn (2002), Matthews (2006) and Bland (2015).

References

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